

Motivation towards Learning Social Studies in a Virtual Environment: A Quantitative Study

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Abstract: Due to the unexpected circumstances brought by the COVID-19 pandemic, all of the life aspects worldwide have been affected from livelihood, economy, and most especially education. Since physical contact with people is strictly prohibited, the majority of the schools and universities worldwide have shifted from traditional learning to online and distance modes of learning, and considering the new mode of learning there were multiple studies that highlight the important role of motivation in the academic performance of the student, especially in a virtual learning environment. Upon reading the literature it can be said that there are studies that still lacking in some aspects and this was due to the differences between respondents, location, and context.

This study utilized the Scale for Motivation Towards Learning Geography adapted from Yildirim (2017), this descriptive-quantitative study aims to determine and understand the level of motivation of students in learning social studies in the virtual environment and to identify if there is a significant difference between students' gender and class level and their motivation to learn about social studies online between the four factors identified by Yildirim (2017) which are interest, confidence, information acquisition, and performance.

The study has a total of 127 college students from Western Mindanao State University who are taking up social studies subjects. The results revealed that respondents have a "High Motivation" and are still motivated amidst the challenges brought by the pandemic. Respondents show that interest, confidence, information acquisition, and performance are still positive even in the virtual learning environment, and the love of learning social studies is still manifested. It was also noted that virtual learning or online learning helps the respondents to continue excelling in the class through a variety of social media apps that help boost their confidence and instill more interest in learning social studies.

Keywords: Academic motivation, Motivation, Online learning, Pandemic, Social science, Social studies, Quantitative study, Virtual environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade, traditional learning occurs in the four corners of the classroom, a physical classroom setting where the student and teachers interact, exchange, and acquire knowledge physically however, the traditional setting of education has transformed into virtual classes due to the unprecedented circumstances brought by the pandemic. The World Health Organization gives the command to every country to shut down its doors and take proper precautions because this is a major health emergency and international concern that must be taken seriously (WHO, 2020). The pandemic has greatly affected our way of life and also every aspect of our society, from businesses, work, the economy, and most especially the educational system. As a result of the alarming increase in COVID-19 cases in the entire Philippines, the government agency headed by the education sectors: The Department of Education, and the Commission on Higher Education have laid out policies and strong implementation of various synchronous and asynchronous classes that have gone through investigation and study for the educational system to still run through even in the pandemic. COVID-19 Pandemic has forced academic institutions, teachers, the student, and concerned stakeholders to revolutionize from traditional learning to distance and virtual learning or also known as "New Normal" (Magsambol, 2021). The traditional face-to-face learning was put to a stop and online blended, synchronous, asynchronous, flexible, modular, and

homeschooling learning become the solution to pursue learning amidst the pandemic (Coman et al., 2020). Since then, many school, college and state universities in the Philippines including our very own Western Mindanao State University switch to online mode to facilitate learning. At the same time, as stated by Omar, Hassan & Atan (2012), the growth of online tools and platforms has tremendously gained popularity that helps aided and become the medium for synchronous and asynchronous classes to happen.

Due to the sudden shift to virtual learning, numerous issues regarding the difficulties and challenges of virtual learning have been known (Rotas & Cahapay, 2020). Researchers Son et al. (2020), found out in their study that students face an increased level of anxiety and study behavioral problem. While Chandra (2020) found out that student in the pandemic have high academic stress due to demands and pressures coming from family, friends and school. On the other hand, the study of Hara & Kling (1999) shows that low internet connection, dissatisfaction, and many other factors related to online learning are one of the frustrations that student face in distance education and all of these are associated on the motivation level of the students. The virtual learning approaches heavily relies on the student's ability to make meanings, create connections and sustain the environment the student is currently in. Thus, motivation plays a very critical role in a positive mind set towards learning as well as self-supervision (Hew & Chiu 2018). Countless research studies have found out that motivation plays a vital role when it comes to learning processes.

According to Seker (2015), the motivation of every person has two types, the external motivation as well as internal motivation. Researchers Deci, Koestner & Ryan, (2001) explained in their study that intrinsic motivation which is also called internal motivation, a type of motivation that develops throughout the situation without thinking about external motives such as rewards. Hence, Ryan & Deci, (2000) pointed out that extrinsic motivation is a type of motivation driven by external forces such as rewards and praises that's why it is also named as external motivation. Paris and Turner, (1994) used the term "engine of learning" to described motivation which means that motivation administers the learner to initiate the right thing by a particular task of subject related matters. It is similar to Hatice (2015) which pointed out that motivation is the key driver of every individual to do things, it guaranteed that students are efficient, resilient, and productive without any feeling of guiltiness or pressure from their immediate environment. In addition, Karakaya & Ay (2007), claimed that every individual has a diverse and independent desire, demand, and expectations due to the differences of environment and the kind of life they are in, although diverse but the capacity of every individual to increase their level motivation happens when their basic needs, wishes, demands as well as expectations are met. As eloquently stated by, Filgona et al. (2020), in every milestone of our life, motivation is one of the vital ingredients to success and that goes the same to education.

Motivating students to do well, despite the challenges brought by the COVID-19 Pandemic is deemed necessary especially with the virtual learning setup that we have right now, and since the teacher is not physically involved with them, the students are independent and not free from distractions and other subject related problems hence keeping them in check and motivated would ensure that they have acquired the knowledge they needed to acquire and most importantly is that they are physically and mentally stable. However, research studies on determining student motivation towards social studies online are scarce. In addition, studies on virtual learning are also limited and are much needed as it greatly affects learner's motivation because they are no longer in a traditional setting which there has been a drastic change and a need for the student to adjust. The challenges imposed by the pandemic in the educational setting have put a lot of increasing value to further enhance the study especially on the context of social studies where there is a scarce of study concerning virtual learning environment. To fill in the research gap, this research study has an objective of determining students' motivation towards learning social studies in a virtual learning environment and employing a quantitative research method. The participants are coming from Western Mindanao State University respectively. Also, it would be a great help and vital source of information to know its implication to help institutions of higher learning, teachers, and concerned stakeholders to deeply understand more the student as well as social studies as a discipline and to further enhance this study for future research use.

Research Question:

- 1) What are the levels of motivation among students when learning social studies online in terms of interest, self-confidence, information acquisition and performance in a virtual learning environment?
- 2) Is there a significant difference on student's level of motivation when they are group according to their gender?
- 3) Is there a significant difference between students' class levels and their motivation to learn about social studies online?

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Motivation in Social Studies

Motivating students to learn is one of the challenging tasks of the teachers and many are struggling with it (Heafner, 2016), and according to Schug et al. (1984), this is frequently prevalent in social studies subjects which is perceived by many of the students as boring and not interesting. This is because of the inherent or natural nature of social studies since it is composed of various disciplines such as history, geography, sociology, and many more that came together and become the umbrella of social studies. It was defined by the NCSS or the national council of social studies that social studies is the study of people, the individuals relation and effect to the world and it is known for focusing on issues in society both in the context of ago society and later society.

An inquiry-based and interdisciplinary subject of many disciplines such as ecology, law, economics, philosophy, ethics, political science, and other social science disciplines. Students think that social studies are not relevant and interesting to learn, thus most of the students who are not inclined in learning social studies are unmotivated to learn and do the task on social studies areas. Motivation is defined by Schunk, Pintrich, and Meece (2008) as a type of drive and process that makes the students goal-oriented and goal-directed, depending on the student's motivation. Motivation is highly important as it will sustain our inner drives in doing the things we need to do. It is pointed out by Schunk (1995), that motivation is not just a drive but it also influences us on how we learn, what are the things we need and want to learn, what we learn, and the things that we want to neglect.

Many educators in the field suggest that the inadequate student's attentiveness in social studies discussion have something to do with the strategies, teaching style, and methods that are used and integrated by the teacher (Martorella, 1997). Thus, knowing the strategies, methods, and styles to use in learning social studies is vital especially for diverse learners who learn differently. Positive interactions and learning experiences are also important for students to not develop fear especially for mostly conventional subject areas such as philosophy and history. And if there was a lack of interactions between learners and instructors aside from the fellow learners the learning of social studies will not be achieved since social studies is more on inquiry base learning (Young, 1997; Burdman, 1998). This method of learning makes the learners go through reverie, being distant, and lack of interaction that would need a deep-rooted will to lessen its effects (Arkorful & Abaidoo, 2014). Hence, this current study ought to understand the motivation of students in learning social studies in the virtual environment and to identify if there is a significant difference between students' gender and their motivation to learn about social studies online.

Virtual learning environment

Since the start of the pandemic, there is a wide interest in studying virtual learning environment. Researchers have given their varied definitions and views on virtual learning environments. Simonson and Schlosser (2006), defined a VLE as a type of learning environment that can be an alternative yet still functional to occur in the absence of a traditional or face-to-face environment. Additionally, according to the agency learning lab (2020), Virtual learning refers to a mode of learning that is totally virtual. This can be considered an efficient tool to utilize considering the current situations that we have. On the other hand, according to Alves et al. (2017), Virtual Learning (VLE) is the outcome of the continuous evolution of technology that we have today, it is not static, but instead, it is a dynamic one. It applies to various changing needs of the society and considers its features and potentialities that would give especially for the students to still be equipped with knowledge amidst the pandemic. Simonson and Schlosser (2006) have pointed out that, one of the features of virtual learning is that it knows no place. Learning in a virtual environment can take place anytime and anywhere, which is convenient, efficient, and advantageous for the student and teachers. Virtual learning can be broadly categorized into online learning which is composed of several forms such as blended learning, flexible learning, internet computer-based learning, which would make the learning continue even amidst the pandemic, and teachers must have the necessary skills to become effective in the virtual platforms because the competence of the teacher when it comes to technology are associated with its attitude in class (Jacinto & Alieto, 2020).

There are several studies conducted on the virtual learning environment and the results differ from one another. Moreover, the research of Martín et al. (2021), which took place in the academic year of 2019-2020, the participants are from the education science of their university respectively. It is a quantitative study and the method of collecting information includes an online questionnaire using simple random sampling. Their study aims to know the views of students regarding

the teachers' strategies and style being adopted in the virtual learning set up by their teachers respectively. Their study shows that the students do not have the knowledge when it comes to the tools and other usages of applications in the virtual learning environment. It indicates greater dissatisfaction about the transition of virtual learning as well as the tutoring functions of the school and teachers among the different learning modes and applications. Their study depicts how important it is that the school, teacher, as well as students, would collaborate and understand together the proper usage of tools and applications in virtual learning with accurate pedagogical strategies used by the teachers.

The mentioned study above shows the dissatisfactions of the student but the next study would show the teachers' views and experiences while in the virtual learning environment. Dahlstrom, Brooks, and Bichsel in their study have concluded that 74% of teachers are satisfied and acknowledged that the kind of virtual environment that they have is a great instrument that will help improve the learning processes. While, 71% of teachers in the study have claimed that a VLE is an appropriate tool for the students to be enriched with knowledge in the virtual classroom. While in the ninety-nine percent of institutions that apply virtual learning environment. 85% of professors have been using the virtual learning environment as a tool in teaching and 56% of teachers have noted that they are using virtual learning daily while 56% of the students said that they use virtual learning environments in most of their course's units. This result shows how they appreciate virtual learning and how this helps them to continue teaching and learning.

Morais, Alves, and Miranda has shown that there are positive indicators in the learners' access to the online environment and there is a significant aspects between the students' capability to access the online world as well as their performance in their respective classes. It is indeed a fact that Technology has become part of our daily lives. It ignites novelty, fantasy, challenges, curiosity and offers new experiences which is essential in cultivating individual motivation (Lepper & Malone, 1987) such as this virtual learning environment. The result of each study varies from one another due to the differences in participants and locations respectively, and despite that, there is a lot of study addressing the students view in the virtual learning environment in relation to motivation, the concerns arise giving unclear and conflicting results, especially to a limited research study in Zamboanga and Western Mindanao State University settings. Furthermore, this research study focuses on determining students' motivation in learning social studies in terms of interest, self-confidence, information acquisition and performance in a virtual learning environment.

Motivation towards Virtual Learning

Technology has changed our lives, and these changes can be significantly experienced in the field of education. The continuous development of technology has resulted in making the virtual environment possible. Technology brings motivation because we use it as a tool for our academic tasks to become easier (Lepper & Malone, 1987). The study of Schaer, Roizard, Christmann, and Lemaitre (2006) demonstrated that e-learning do not affect the allotted time of teaching, instead it promotes active participation of the students. Their collective experience affects e-learning and brings positive influence (Wan, Wang & Haggerty, 2008).

Motivation according to Paris and Turner (1994) is like a type of engine that makes individual to drive its will. It brings impact to what will the student learn and how they want to learn (Schunk & Usher, 2012). This plays a major role as it reflects their persistence in completing the course as well as their progress. Being familiar with motivation and its various factors that influence the learners bespeak importance in the implications that can be realized in the teaching and learning processes. It was said that the motivation in the learning of the students spans from intrinsic to extrinsic motivation that is gleaned from self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Through interest, excitement, confidence, and learning activities, learners can be motivated intrinsically (Ryan & Deci, 2000). While several external factors may affect their motivation extrinsically (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Learners that are immersed in learning likely produce higher quality of learning and with motivation involved (Figueira & Duarte, 2011).

Motivation brings a lot of impact in virtual learning because motivation according to Brophy is a vital factor in growth and learning of the students. It has been pointed out by Muilenburg and Berge (2005), that one reason for students dropping out from their online class is their poor motivation. However, despite that, there is a lot of research addressing student's motivation with the new mode of teaching being implemented fueled by technology there are still unclear and inadequate reasons in line with motivation towards virtual learning that need to be fulfilled such as the study of Schaer, Roizard, Christmann, and Lemaitre (2006) that I have mentioned above, the effectiveness of e-learning might be different due to some factors such as the type of learners, the technology utilized, location and most especially the students motivation. Furthermore, this research study focuses on determining students' motivation in learning social studies in a

virtual environment and to see if there is a significant difference between students' class levels and their motivation to learn about social studies online.

III. METHODOLOGY

Respondents of the Study

The sample size of this study is composed of 127 college students from Western Mindanao State University who are taking up social studies subjects. In terms of gender distribution, the majority of the respondents are female (78 or 60.9%). Moreover, the data gathered in regards to the age ranges from 18-23 years old. The youngest reported is aged 18 (Three or 2.3%), on the other hand the oldest reported is aged 23 (Six or 4.7%), with mean age of 20.51 (standard deviation = 1.167). Meanwhile, for the year level, the least declared respondents are 1st year students (30 or 23.4%), while the most declared respondents are 2nd year students (35 or 27.3%), the year level have a mean score of 2.50 (standard deviation = 1.105).

Research Design

The study makes use of a descriptive research design. Quantitative research collects and analyses accumulated numerical data (Bhandari, 2020). Moreover, the study utilizes a survey questionnaire for gathering statistical information about attributes, attitudes, or actions of a population by a structural set of questions. In relation to this, the utilization of questionnaires answerable by Likert Scale consists of a series of actions which are indicators of the latent traits. In fact, using this is easily understood. Additionally, employing questionnaires answerable by Likert Scale make relative and absolute judgments about measures of attitude (Maeda, 2014). Finally, there was no manipulation done in any of the variables and respondents were assigned non-randomly (O'Dwyer & Bernauer, 2013).

Research Instrument

The study utilized the Scale for Motivation towards Learning Geography that was adapted from the work of Yildirim (2017) in determining student's motivation. The researcher have modified the original questionnaires to incline its context to the current study and the appropriateness of the tool. The modification includes the alteration of the subject Geography to Social Studies and context like face to face environment to virtual learning environment. Moreover, the instrument has 22 items that are divided into four distinct sub factors (interest, confidence, information acquisition, and performance) that entails a five-point Likert scale from strongly agree down to strongly disagree which was developed by Kaya (2013). The distribution of the items are: Interest (1-2-3-4-5-6), Confidence (7-8-9-10-11), Information Acquisition (1-2-13-14-15-16-17-18), and Performance (19-20-21-22).

Reliability of the Instrument

The instrument was administered to a total of 32 respondents who will not formed part of the final sampling frame. The sample for pilot testing constitute 68.8% females and with 62.5% 3rd year student who dominated the population. To determine the reliability of the instrument Chronbach's alpha's test was used. Hence, the following reliability was yielded for the different subscales. For Interest subscale the result of the reliability is (Cronbach' $\alpha = 0.77$), while for Confidence subscale the result of the reliability is (Cronbach' $\alpha = 0.74$), on the other hand for Information acquisition subscale it shows that it has a reliability of (Cronbach' $\alpha = 0.75$), while for the last one which is the Performance subscale has a reliability of (Cronbach' $\alpha = 0.74$). To determine the reliability of the whole instrument Chronbach's alpha's test was also utilized and yielded the result of the reliability (Cronbach' $\alpha = 0.87$) which shows that it is valid and reliable.

IV. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This section of the study presents the results and analyses of the data. Moreover, discussion and interpretation are likewise presented.

Results

Academic Motivation Level of the Respondents: Interest Factor

To discern the respondents' motivation towards learning Social Studies in a virtual environment, the responses were exported and transferred to SPSS. This is to enable the treatment of the data using descriptive statistics, specifically mean and standard deviation. Moreover, it was interpreted by a developed scale employing equal intervals. Table 1.0 presents the analysis of the data. Included in the table are the responses of the respondents in every item of the questionnaire

(frequencies and equivalent percentages), mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and interpretation (Interp.) — 1.0-1.79 (Very Low Motivation [VLM]), 1.80-2.59 (Low Motivation [LM]), 2.60-3.39 (Moderate [MR]), 3.40-4.19 (High Motivation [HM]), 4.20-5.0 (Very High Motivation [VHM]).

Table 1: Respondent's level of Motivation: Interest Factor

#	Statements	Responses												Interp
		SA		A		U		DA		SD		M	SD	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%			
1	The subject of social studies in online set up is interesting to me.	59	46.1	34	26.6	19	14.8	11	8.6	4	3.1	4.04	1.11	HM
2	Any kind of document related to social studies is interesting to me.	55	43.0	48	37.5	13	10.2	8	6.3	3	2.3	4.13	0.99	HM
3	I would like to know about prominent social scientists.	57	44.5	41	32.0	22	17.2	2	1.6	5	3.9	4.12	1.01	HM
4	I would like to take part in activities about social studies online.	50	39.1	41	32.0	28	22.9	8	6.3	0	0	4.04	0.93	HM
5	I prefer e-books on social studies when I choose an e-book.	39	30.5	36	28.1	32	25.0	17	13.4	3	2.3	3.71	1.11	HM
6	Social studies is interesting to me because it relates to current events.	61	47.7	42	32.8	13	10.2	7	5.5	4	3.1	4.17	1.03	VHM
Overall Level of Motivation in Interest Factor												4.04	0.82	HM

The descriptive analysis of the data provided in Table 1.0 shows that out of the six listed statement for interest sub factor, 5 of which shows 'High Motivation' while for the last item which states (Social studies is interesting to me because it relates to current events) has a 'Very High Motivation' (M=4.17, SD=1.03). It could be deduced from Table 1.0 that the mean from the scale of determining level of motivation in virtual environment is 4.04 which indicates that respondents who have encountered the subject Social Studies have a 'High Motivation' when it comes to interest factor in the virtual environment. Despite the prevalent circumstances brought by the pandemic, the result denounces that learning social studies in a virtual environment sparks respondent's interest.

These result conforms to the findings of Deci and Ryan (2002), wherein they found out that interest is one basic and important factor of intrinsic motivation and that it serves as a drive for individual to have full independent decisions and most importantly self-direction towards his study. It can be denote from the data presented that item 5 (I prefer e-books on social studies when I choose an e-book) has the lowest mean score (M=3.1, SD=1.11), this reflects Casselden et al. (2020), where they have found out that using e-book includes stress and frustrations especially on the level of complexity when it comes to the provision as well as the different publishers restrictions and most of all the incompatibility in devices among student readers. Aside from that problems such as old data publications and lack of subject areas in e-books are also found in their findings.

Other studies that also support this study are (Hobbs & Klare, 2016; Jeong, 2012; Li, 2016; Marques, 2012; Wu and Chen, 2011) which includes eye strain as one of the negative impact when reading electronic book, moreover (Li, 2016;

Berg et al. 2010; Hobbs & Klare, 2016) all denotes in their respective findings that e-books may be a barrier to achieve active learning this is because of the distraction that the students can get while reading e-books such as popping of notifications and messages on various social media platforms considering the short attention span of the students. Although item 5 is the lowest in terms of mean score but it also receives 'High Motivation', which means that the result of some researches above are in opposite with the findings of Rowlands et.al (2009), where their findings shows that e-book are already part of educational mainstream and it sparks interest among students especially in the digitalized age.

This also mirrors with the findings of Richter (2021) which finds out that e-book is the most preferable type of book especially in the digital age. The purchase of e-book for educational and entertainment purposes ranks most in Germany with 58% and rank second in Asia and greater part of it is Japan with 40.1%, followed by South Korea with 34.6, China with 32% and other southeast Asian nation such as the Philippines. These findings shows that e-books are the preferable ones when it comes to educational sources.

Moreover, item 1 'The subject of social studies in online set up is interesting to me' has a mean score of 4.04 and SD-1.11, with interpretation of 'High Motivation'. It was highlight by (Lee, Stringer, & Du, 2017; Mann & Henneberry, 2012), that learning in online set up drives students motivation as they became flexible in the task that they have and it is more convenient to them to have a class online rather than the traditional one, majority of the responses in their study have stated that they found online learning as flexible and suitable for their needs. It was then supported by Liaw and Huang (2013) that students prefer the online set up because students now a days have 'online social comfort' where they found it easy to maneuver social media apps and technology related to teaching. And for the item 4 'I would like to take part in activities about social studies online' was in tie with item 1 which also have the same mean score of 4.04 (SD-0.93) and also have an interpretation of 'High Motivation'. According to the study of Ryan et al. (2002), social studies activities are engaging enough since social studies involves a lot of disciplines who came together to form the social studies curriculum. Social studies activities such as diorama, landscaping, trends and issues for peer collaboration are one of the factor that makes social studies activities more engaging. This was also supported by Tobias (1994) who found out that social studies activities encourage motivation and interest, they also found out that students prefer activities that would enhance their confidence and make collaboration with the other.

On another note, the data also shows that item 2 'Any kind of document related to social studies is interesting to me' has a mean score (4.13, SD- .991) and interpreted as 'High Motivation'. This result is in line with the study of Renninger (2016), which emphasized that knowledge are interconnected with interest in either past or present documents that are related to programs such as social studies. Moreover, (Alexander, Kulikowich, & Jetton, 1994; Tobias, 1994), states that interest also involves loving about topics that are related ones course that be beneficial to you as a learner. Moreover, Item 3 'I would like to know about prominent social scientists' has a mean score of 3.97 and SD- 1.105, interpreted as 'High Motivation'. Tobias (1994) have found out that learners who have inner curiosity regarding personalities such as proponent of theories and studies, scientist biography and many more that are involve in their own program have an innate interest, this interest are related to their ability to continue learning and to learn people that drives their curiosity. The study on students' Interest in Social Studies and Negotiation Self-Efficacy have also showed that curiosity helps inner motivation and that inner motivation ignites interest on learning social studies, and studying social scientist helps learners to be more interest on social studies (Yukhymenko, 2011).

Intriguingly, it could be noted that in item 6 (Social studies is interesting to me because it relates to current events) has a mean score of 4.32 (SD-0.93) and an interpretation of 'Very High Motivation', the highest one among other 5 items. The NCSS or National council for social studies have emphasized that social studies curriculum is an integrative curriculum which revolves around the social events in the real life. Moreover, Harackiewicz et al. (2016), found out that teachers strategies in motivating student helps students to have high interest to their studies, this involves context provoking lessons and experiential learning in the issues present in the society, student became more interested to learning social studies because it relates to the present issues in the society. Deci and Ryan (2002), also clarified on their study that students have a high interest in learning social studies because of its curriculum that offers application on real life events such as the discipline of political science, history, sociology, law and many more.

Even amidst the challenges imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic such as loss of interest towards studying online, anxiety on virtual environment, high levels of disinterest in learning and more but the respondents shows that learning social studies becomes more interesting even though it's on a virtual environment. Overall, the analysis of the data depicts that

respondents have a 'High Motivation', with a mean score of 4.00 (SD- .814). It can be reflected here that students are still motivated and still interested towards learning social studies in a virtual environment. Studies such as of Alves et al. (2017), supported this result and shows on their findings that students who are learning in a virtual environment are more likely to be more interested to the course that they are studying for three main reasons, first is the flexibility that virtual environment would gave, second sources are readily available on the internet and lastly students prefer the virtual environment more compare to the traditional face-to-face. Deci and Ryan (2002), added that the findings of interest as one important factor to learn ignites individual autonomy. Moreover, this findings also reflect with the study of Harackiewicz et al. (2016), where their findings denotes that interest is a very powerful factor for motivational process as it boost students sense of self direction towards their studies, guides their academic path and enables their mental condition for active learning.

Academic Motivation Level of the Respondents: Confidence Factor

To determine the academic motivation of the respondents in the confidence factor, the responses from the Motivation towards learning Social Studies in a Virtual Environment questionnaire were coded and encoded initially in a spreadsheet. Descriptive statistics were performed to analyze the data presented in Table 1.2. Included in the presentation are the responses in every item of the questionnaire (frequencies and equivalent percentages), mean (M), and interpretation (Interp.) - 1.0-1.79 (Very Low Motivation [VLM]), 1.80-2.59 (Low Motivation [LM]), 2.60-3.39 (Moderate [MR]), 3.40-4.19 (High Motivation [HM]), 4.20-5.0 (Very High Motivation [VHM]).

Table 1.1: Respondent's level of Motivation: Confidence Factor

#	Statements	Responses												Interp
		SA		A		U		DA		SD		M	SD	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%			
7	I believe that I will get a high score in my online social studies lesson	53	41.4	38	29.7	22	17.2	12	9.4	2	1.6	4.00	1.05	HM
8	I am confident when I talk about social studies online.	44	34.4	39	30.5	24	18.8	18	14.1	2	1.6	3.82	1.10	HM
9	I am sure I will understand whether the subject of social studies is easy or not.	50	39.1	46	35.9	20	15.6	8	6.3	3	2.3	4.03	1.01	HM
10	I believe that I will be successful in my online social studies examination.	46	35.9	35	27.3	33	25.8	11	8.6	2	1.6	3.88	1.05	HM
11	I trust myself when I participate in my online social studies lesson.	51	39.8	46	35.9	15	11.7	11	8.6	4	3.1	4.01	1.07	HM
Overall Level of Motivation in Confidence Factor												3.96	0.87	HM

The analysis of the data presented in Table 1.1 points out that the respondents, generally, were found to be possessing 'High Motivation' (M = 3.96, SD- 0.87). This suggests that the respondents have high motivation when it comes to confidence factor. Detailed analysis of the data in item nine (I am sure I will understand whether the subject of social studies is easy or not), provides that 39.1 % of the respondents reported to have 'High Motivation', this item is the second highest in terms of mean score (M= 4.03, SD- 1.01). It can be deduced here that respondents have a definite knowledge towards the different subject areas that the social studies program have. This result conforms to the findings of Foskett et al. (2004), who argued that students have the ability to assess whether or not the subject that they are

encountering with are easy or not. This is also similar to the study of Garratt (1986) and Jin et al. (2011), that students who are going to enroll in a course have the adequate knowledge on how easy or challenging that their course would be and it is one factor that students are considering before choosing a course. Moreover, Tripney et al. (2010), Rodeiro (2007) and Weeden (2007) also perceived that having an understanding on how challenging their course is would improve their confidence and interest to their chosen course.

It can be notice from the data that item 11 (I trust myself when I participate in my online social studies lesson) are the second highest among the list with a mean score of 4.01 (SD- 1.07) and interpreted as 'High Motivation'. This result corroborate with the findings of Engle and Ochoa (1988) which claimed that participation in class involves self-confidence and self-efficacy. He compare the social participation in the context of society and self-participation in the context of studying social studies, he argued that when we participate in the society we also learn to participate in class and vice versa and boost our confidence by solving social issues. This was in consonant with the findings of (Hanks, 1981; Holland & Andre, 1987), where they stated that participation in the classroom improves ones confidence and even improve social participation. Lindsay (1984) and Milbarth and Goel (1979) both also see the connection between self-participation and social partition and added that self-confidence and willingness to answer in the discussion is a great step towards attaining high self-esteem and that social studies activities must continue to include skills such as decision making skills for social participation, critical thinking and problem solving skills for solving social issues on their immediate environment.

Meanwhile, item 7 (I believe that I will get a high score in my online social studies lesson) is the third highest on the confidence factor (M= 4.00, SD- 1.05), 41.4% of the respondents has chosen 'Strongly agree' on the said statement. On the other hand, item 10 followed (I believe that I will be successful in my online social studies examination) with a mean score of 3.88 (SD- 1.05), and both have an interpretation of High Motivation'. In line with this is the study of Joe et al (2022), wherein they have found out that students have high motivation due to the confidence in using MS teams and other online applications. It can be said that respondents have high self-efficacy towards learning social studies in a virtual environment and are confident on their academic scores. This result are similar to the theory of Bandura (1986), wherein students who believe in themselves that they will be successful on a certain matter such as exams are result of their experiences in life. Students who experiences strong confidence believed to have positive cognitive determinants and most likely be successful in their academic studies. This result is in congruent with the study of Akbari et al. (2020) from Kandahar University, which shows on their result that students' academic performance is greatly affected by their level of confidence. Akbari et al. (2020) added that confidence would pertains to one's own ability to accomplish set of task and believing to one's ability is an important factor for academic success.

Furthermore, among all the items, item 8 (I am confident when I talk about social studies online), got the lowest mean score of 3.69 (SD- 1.187), although this was the lowest among all the items but it also has an interpretation of 'High Motivation', which means that respondents is still motivated on this specific item. It was noted in the study of Holland and Andre (1987), that student's confidence varies on their ability to acquire knowledge, self-interest and the ability to maneuver educational technology in the virtual environment. This was similar to the findings of Brophy (2008), that technological access and interest to attend online classes affects the confidence of the students. Jacobson (2022), concluded that children are greatly affected by the social media and technological apps especially in these times of pandemic. Ferlazzo (2020), said that teachers must learn to apply technology and boost the student's confidence while integrating social studies activities. Moreover, item 8 still have an interpretation of 'High Motivation', Ballane (2019) believes that the students of today will be able to boost their confidence with the use of technology and be highly motivated while learning social studies.

Overall, respondents shows 'High Motivation' for the confidence factor (M= 3.96, SD- 0.87), this shows that even in the virtual environment, students confidence is still the same and are not affected by the transition of learning modality as well as the pandemic, students still sparks confidence within them. This was in line with the findings of Holland and Andre (1987), which found out on their findings that confidence is an important factor to motivation, high confidence would result to high motivation. Ferlazzo (2020), added that with teachers continuous encouragement and teaching of social studies approaches in virtual environment, students confidence will continue to sparks as they are consider as students living in the digital age, and that pandemic would continue to be a contributing factor to be confident on their social studies classes.

Academic Motivation Level of the Respondents: Information acquisition Factor

To determine the academic level of the respondents in the information acquisition factor, the responses from the Motivation towards learning Social Studies in a Virtual Environment questionnaire were coded and entered into a spreadsheet prior to analysis using the SPSS. The raw data were treated with descriptive statistics. Analysis is presented in Table 1.2. Included in the presentation are frequencies and percentages of responses across used scale in the instrument, the mean scores and interpretation - 1.0-1.79 (Very Low Motivation [VLM]), 1.80-2.59 (Low Motivation [LM]), 2.60-3.39 (Moderate [MR]), 3.40-4.19 (High Motivation [HM]), 4.20-5.0 (Very High Motivation [VHM]).

Table 1.2: Respondent's level of Motivation: Information acquisition Factor

#	Statements	Responses										Interp.		
		SA		A		U		DA		SD			M	SD
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%			
12	I would like to learn about developments in social studies online	57	44.5	47	36.7	12	9.4	7	5.5	4	3.1	4.14	1.01	HM
13	I would like my teacher to give a more detailed explanation during the online social studies lesson.	68	53.1	35	27.3	17	14.3	5	3.9	2	1.6	4.27	0.94	VHM
14	I would like to investigate the causes and consequences of current social studies events online.	59	46.1	39	30.5	13	10.2	13	10.2	3	2.3	4.08	1.09	HM
15	I would like to have access to many sources related to social studies.	59	46.1	43	33.6	16	12.5	6	4.7	3	2.3	4.17	0.98	HM
16	I want to exchange information about my knowledge of social studies with my friends in a virtual learning environment.	50	39.1	38	29.7	21	16.4	15	11.7	3	2.3	3.92	1.11	HM
17	I want to receive online homework in order to learn more about social studies.	43	33.6	26	20.3	32	25.0	19	14.8	7	5.5	3.62	1.24	HM
18	I also want to learn about social studies subjects that are not taught in school.	63	49.2	45	35.2	9	7.0	6	4.7	4	3.1	4.23	0.99	VHM
Overall Level of Motivation in Information Acquisition Factor												4.07	0.84	HM

The data in table 1.2 presents the 7 item for the information acquisition factor. The descriptive analysis of the data in table 1.2 shows that respondents are highly motivated with an interpretation of 'High Motivation' (M= 4.07, SD- 0.84), two item got a 'Very High Motivation' interpretation which is item 13 (I would like my teacher to give a more detailed explanation during the online social studies lesson) and item 18 (I also want to learn about social studies subjects that are not taught in school), while other 5 items on the information acquisition receives an interpretation of 'High Motivation'. Information acquisition is very important according to Sarit et al (2007), because it makes the knowledge more systematized. Information acquisition is also became the part of academic motivation. Moreover, it can be infer from the descriptive analysis of the data that the lowest one is item 17 (I want to receive online homework in order to learn more about social studies) with a mean score of 3.62 (SD- 1.24).

There are many studies who shares the same result as item 17 such the study of Ferlazzo (2020), where it stated that students would prefer more the activities conducted in synchronous classes rather than asynchronous classes, it was also proven in their study that students are having hard time in managing online homework. This findings are also in consonant with the findings of Josh (2017), where it depicts that students do not want to have online homework, as they are already bombarded by many activities on synchronous classes on many subjects, it was also found out on their study that too much online homework does not result to adequate acquisition of knowledge. In addition, Hauk and Segalla (2005), found out that traditional homework are more effective rather than online homework. Although item 17 is the lowest one among the other item but it has a 'High Motivation' interpretation which means that student are still motivated and there are just some factor why it received the lowest among all items.

Furthermore, countless studies also show that homework increases students' knowledge and it is in support with the findings of 'High Motivation' in item 17. Based on the findings of Weimer (2013), it was revealed that the online homework makes the student more productive on learning and it encourages self-direction to their study. In addition, students shows high appreciation towards the online homework system and said that it promotes growth for them as a learner. Ferlazzo (2020), have stated that differences in homework or learning space, network connection access and availability as well as types of learner are some of the factors why results on information acquisition varies.

Furthermore, item 16 (I want to exchange information about my knowledge of social studies with my friends in a virtual learning environment) receives a total mean score of 3.92 (SD- 1.11) and interpreted as 'High Motivation'. Claiborne et al. (2020), have found out that students love to share and exchange information with their friends and they call this process as 'teaching outside classroom', where students learn through exchanging of information, they also described this as a unique way of learning. It was similar with the study of Larsen et al. (2017), they said that 21st students unique way of information acquisition is not just through their teachers but also through technology and their immediate environment such as friends and family. Ryan and Deci (2017), also agrees that sharing knowledge enhance and fosters communication, and strengthen the foundation of knowledge which makes it long term.

Item 14th on the other hand (I would like to investigate the causes and consequences of current social studies events online) is also interpreted as 'High Motivation', (M= 4.08, SD- 1.09). Social studies is based on integrated curriculum, and type of learners in a social studies class are expected to be investigative and curious driven (NCSS, 2019). This result was also in line with the findings of Lee et al. (2017), where they found out that students in a diverse social studies classroom are more concern with the current social events and determine its cause and consequences. The data also depicts that item 12 (I would like to learn about developments in social studies online) has a mean score of 4.14 (SD- 1.01), it was clarified by the National council for social studies that social studies curriculum involves development on the society and be able to integrate that in the curriculum and students taking social studies must also be concern on the development on their own environment (NCSS, 2019). Furthermore, Schunk (2012) have stated that students who loves social studies are much concern to every issues and development on their immediate environment.

While item 15 'I would like to have access to many sources related to social studies' (M= 4.17, SD- 0.98) and also characterized as 'High Motivation'. Access to sources are vital when it comes to social studies, especially for the discipline that requires utmost reading such as history, anthropology, political science, law and many more (Schunk, 2012). It was supported by Jetton (1994), wherein they show that information acquisition is a vital factor for interest and motivation, this include the access to sources for their lessons and topics that concerns them. The second highest on the item of information acquisition factor is item 13 'I would like my teacher to give a more detailed explanation during the online social studies lesson', (M= 4.27, SD- 0.94) and an interpretation of 'Very High Motivation'.

This was the highest among all of the item because teacher's explanation is very crucial to learning especially when it's on a virtual environment. This conforms to the findings of Sun (2008), wherein their findings dictates that among the factors 'difficulty of the lesson, teachers explanation, access to device, access to technology, the highest among all of them is the teachers explanation. This just shows how important the role of a teacher is and the accuracy of its explanation. Overall, the respondents shows 'High Motivation' (M= 4.07, SD- 0.84) in terms of information acquisition factor. It can be deduced that respondent's information acquisition are not affected by the current mode of learning which is the virtual environment or online learning. This result was supported by Alsalhi et al. (2019), wherein their findings shows that information acquisition improves learning motivation and the higher information that they acquired, the higher the academic success would be. Moreover, this also conforms to the findings of Arkorful and Abaidoo (2014), where

they stated that information acquisition and motivation are link together, and information acquisition is one important ingredients to motivation.

Academic Motivation Level of the Respondents: Performance Factor

To determine the academic level of the respondents in the performance factor, the responses from the Motivation towards learning Social Studies in a Virtual Environment questionnaire were coded and entered into a spreadsheet prior to analysis using the SPSS. The raw data were treated with descriptive statistics. Analysis is presented in Table 1.2 Included in the presentation are frequencies and percentages of responses across used scale in the instrument, the mean scores and interpretation - 1.0-1.79 (Very Low Motivation [VLM]), 1.80-2.59 (Low Motivation [LM]), 2.60-3.39 (Moderate [MR]), 3.40-4.19 (High Motivation [HM]), 4.20-5.0 (Very High Motivation [VHM]).

Table 1.3: Respondent's level of Motivation: Performance Factor

#	Statements	Responses												Interp
		SA		A		U		DA		SD		M	SD	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%			
19	I would like to get the highest grade in my online social studies examination.	69	53.9	30	23.4	20	15.6	4	3.1	4	3.1	4.22	1.03	VHM
20	I want to be able to answer every question about social studies.	62	48.4	43	33.6	15	11.7	4	3.1	3	2.3	4.23	0.94	VHM
21	I want to be the best in all kinds of activities related to social studies.	60	46.9	42	32.8	12	9.4	9	7.0	4	3.1	4.14	1.05	HM
22	I would like to answer every question about social studies that no one knows the answer to.	56	43.8	39	30.5	24	18.8	4	3.1	4	3.1	4.09	1.01	HM
Overall Level of Motivation in Performance Factor												4.18	0.84	HM

The data in table 1.3 presents the four items for the performance factor. The descriptive analysis of the data in table 1.3 shows that two of the item got a 'Very High Motivation' interpretation and the other two item has an interpretation of 'High Motivation'. The overall level of motivation in performance factor is 4.18 (SD- 0.84) and interpreted as 'High Motivation'. Performance is one important factor in motivation, performance in the virtual environment is one of the aspect that is being measured whether or not students acquired the skills and knowledge that they must achieve. The descriptive analysis in table 1.3 shows that item 22 (I would like to answer every question about social studies that no one knows the answer to), Item 22 is the least in terms of mean score (M=4.09, SD- 1.01) and an interpretation of 'High Motivation'.

Meanwhile, item 21 ranked third (I want to be the best in all kinds of activities related to social studies), with a mean score of 4.14 (SD- 1.05) and a verbal interpretation of 'High Motivation'. This was in line with the study of Reuell (2019) from the University of Harvard, their findings show that self-efficacy thinking of the student improves their motivation towards learning, and having a mindset of achieving your goal would result to a positive outcome. Moreover, this was supported by Tobias (1994), wherein he have highlighted that having a positive outlook increases academic level of motivation. On the other hand, item 19 ranked second 'I would like to get the highest grade in my online social studies examination' (M=4.22, SD- 1.03) and a 'Very High Motivation' interpretation. It is the dream and goal of every student to have a highest grade in exams and having a high exam results would boost student's interest and confidence to learn.

This was in consonant with Martinovich (2017) findings. He found out that students from Stanford University have a high motivation in getting a high examination scores, he also found out that academic performance of the student must be prioritize by teachers as it one indicator of academic success. Lastly, it can be notice in item 20 (I want to be able to answer every question about social studies) that it is the highest one in terms of mean score 4.23 (SD- 0.94), and ‘Very High Motivation’ interpretation. This result mirrors the result of Ludlow (2022) where he stated that participation in social studies class increases one’s own motivation.

Moreover, Holland et al (1987), have found out on their study that being able to answer question related to social studies enhances self-efficacy and motivates them to learn more. Moreover, they also stated that even though students would not be able to answer all the question, this will give them an opportunity to gain insight and reflection that they must be able to learn those social studies related questions. Overall, it could be conclude that students have ‘High Motivation’ when it comes to performance factor (M= 4.18, SD- 0.84). Amidst the pandemic, the performance of the student are still an important factor to consider in motivation. This result conforms to the study conducted by Savage (2019), they have concluded that student performance in a virtual learning environment matters and high level of performance during classes would make the students more motivated. In addition, in the study of Carl et al. (2017), stated that performance is an important factor for motivation as well as important educational tool for assessment and evaluation.

Academic Motivation Level of the Respondents: Overall level of Motivation

To determine the overall level of motivation of the respondents, the responses from the Motivation towards learning Social Studies in a Virtual Environment questionnaire were performed to analyze the data through SPSS, the data was achieved through adding the four sub factor in motivation, namely: interest, confidence, information acquisition, and performance. The data presented in table 1.4 are the responses in every overall item of the sub factors mean, the total sample size of this study (N), mean (M), standard deviation (SD) and interpretation (Interp.)- 1.0-1.79 (Very Low Motivation [VLM]), 1.80-2.59 (Low Motivation [LM]), 2.60-3.39 (Moderate [MR]), 3.40-4.19 (High Motivation [HM]), 4.20-5.0 (Very High Motivation [VHM]).

Table 1.4: Respondent’s Overall level of Motivation

Subscales	N	Mean	SD	Interp.
Interest (INT)	127	4.04	0.82	HM
Confidence (CON)	127	3.96	0.87	HM
Information Acquisition (INFAQ)	127	4.07	0.84	HM
Performance (PER)	127	4.18	0.84	HM
Overall motivation level	127	4.06	0.78	HM

The descriptive analysis of the data in table 1.4 shows that all of the subscales are interpreted as ‘High Motivation’. The confidence sub factor got the lowest mean among the four sub scales (M= 3.96, SD- 0.87) with ‘High Motivation’ interpretation, this means that confidence are vital since it has ‘High Motivation’. In the study conducted by Negumbo (2017), they have clarified that confidence plays a vital role in the motivation process of the student even it rank third on the list of factors in their study but confidence role are crucial as it serves as a driven inner thought for students to do well in their academic career. While, Akish (2012) have argued that confidence helps schools and students to prevent dropout rates and ensures that student maintain their interest in learning. On the other hand, the second least among the subscales is the ‘Interest’ sub scale with an interpretation of ‘High Motivation’ and a mean score of 4.04 (SD- 0.82).

Just like confidence, interest is also important and even it is the second least it has an interpretation of ‘High Motivation’. In the study conducted by Harackiewicz et al. (2016), they argued that interest matters and it is an important tool of maintaining the value of education in the society. They added that interest is a powerful factor for motivational processes that guides not just attitude towards learning but also their self-direction and motivation to learn. Moreover, this was supported by Renninger (2016), which states that when promoting interest to the learners, it will result to a more engaged,

motivated and a meaningful teaching and learning experiences with the students. The data in table 1.4 also shows that 'Information Acquisition' is the second highest with (M= 4.07, SD- 0.84). This result agrees with the study conducted by Heese (2019), wherein she found out that information acquisition is more important than any other sub factors under the category of motivation such as perceived choice, pressure and many more.

Heese (2019), also emphasized that Information Acquisition not only helps in motivation but also in social decisions. Intriguingly, the 'Performance' sub scale is the highest among all with a mean score of 4.18 (SD- 0.84). It was stated by Kusurkar (2012), that academic performance affects academic motivation and vice versa, he added that it also affect the other factors such as the interest, confidence and information acquisition. Kusurkar (2012), argued that without the goal of performance there will be no interest to learn, no confidence to build and no information to acquire. Gbollie et al. (2017), study are also similar with Kusurkar (2012), he pointed out that academic performance and motivation have a great relationship to each other such as involving the other factors: self-regulated, self-efficacy and involving strategies when it comes to learning, and performance is considered to be a vital recipe for motivation. Overall, the respondents shows 'High Motivation' (M= 4.06, SD- 0.78), towards learning social studies in the virtual environment. Even amidst the pandemic and the challenges brought by it, respondents are highly motivated in all of these factors: interest, confidence, information acquisition and performance.

Gender differences on the Level of Academic Motivation

To determine whether there is a significant difference on the level of academic motivation towards learning social studies in a virtual environment across gender (male and female) in the four sub factors and the overall result, the data was treated with the parametric statistical tool known Independent samples T-test. The result of the test provides that the alpha value is greater than 0.05 suggesting that data is normally distributed. Table 2.0 gives the independent-samples T-test analysis of the data set.

Table 2: Independent Samples T-test for Gender Differences in Motivation

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig. (2-tailed)
INTEREST	Male	49	4.18	0.84	0.132
	Female	77	3.95	0.79	
CONFIDENCE	Male	49	4.11	0.84	0.131
	Female	77	3.86	0.89	
INFORMATION ACQUISITION	Male	49	4.16	0.90	0.331
	Female	77	4.01	0.80	
PERFORMANCE	Male	49	4.21	0.84	0.683
	Female	77	4.15	0.85	
Overall	Male	49	4.17	0.81	0.235
	Female	63	3.99	0.76	

It could be inferred from the analysis presented in Table 2.0 that gender is not a factor influencing difference on level of motivation towards learning social studies in a virtual environment (sig. value = 0.235 > α = 0.05). Moreover, it could be noticed that males are a have a higher mean compare to female in all of the four factors this is because males are the least respondents, moreover standard deviation from all of the four factors also are close enough that runs from 0.76 to 0.90, this means that the scores are not that dispersed. For the interest factor, the males have a mean score of 4.18 (SD- 0.84), while females have (M= 3.95, SD- 0.79). The data shows in table 1.2 that there is no significant difference in terms of interest across gender (sig. value = 0.132 > α = 0.05). Gender is not significant especially when it comes to interest and motivation to learn (Pesidas et al., 2022). Therefore, the researcher concludes that interest is a factor that drives motivation and it is not associated with gender. This result conforms with the findings of Diekman et al. (2011), where their results shows that interest do not significantly differ when it comes to academic motivation some of the factors involved are learning environment, academic orientation and level of motivation. The independent samples T-test also shows that there is no significant difference when it comes to confidence factor (sig. value = 0.131 > α = 0.05). Males have a mean score of (M= 4.11, SD 0.84), while females (M= 3.8 6, SD- 0.89). The researcher deduced that confidence do not differ when it comes to academic motivation.

The study conducted by Zenger (2018), shows that confidence serves as a drive to motivation and that gender may not serve as a difference to confidence, he added that confidence to learn varies on gender depending on the kind of environment that students are currently in. Meanwhile, it can be infer from the data that information acquisition also shows no significant difference (sig. value = $0.331 > \alpha = 0.05$), male have a (M= 4.16, SD 0.90), females (M= 4.01, SD- 0.80). The researcher deduced that information acquisition have no significant difference towards learning social studies in a virtual environment. This result support the previous findings of Guillen (2018), where it shows that males and females received the same information in online set up. Moreover, for the performance factor, female have a (M= 4.15, SD 0.85), males (M= 4.21, SD- 0.84). It shows no significant difference (sig. value = $0.683 > \alpha = 0.05$).

The researcher conclude that significant difference in performance on previous findings may just be a chance. This was similar to the result of Akiri (2008), where performance in classes are the same since teachers give the same task to both male and female. Moreover, this was in counterpart with the result of Hamdam (2010), where it stated that performance may be the same in terms of output but the level of performance exerted by male and females are different. For the overall, male have a mean score of (M= 4.17, SD 0.81), on the other hand females (M= 3.99, SD- 0.76). The researcher conclude that there is no significant difference in the overall factor towards learning social studies in a virtual environment because (sig. value = $0.235 > \alpha = 0.05$) the student encounters the same subject area, and this result are in consonant with the findings of where their study also shows that student learning social studies subjects encounters the same subject area all the time such as philosophy, history, geography and more.

Results of One-way ANOVA for Difference in Levels of Motivation when participants are grouped according to Year Level

To determine whether there is a significant difference or not on the on the level of academic motivation towards learning social studies in a virtual environment across sub factors when data are grouped according to year level, the data set was subjected to an inferential statistics known as one-way ANOVA. The result of the test is shown in Table 3.0.

Table 3: Academic Level of Motivation when group according to Year Level across Interest factor

	<u>Mean Square</u>	<u>Sig.</u> (2-tailed)	<u>Interpretation</u>
Between Groups	10.803	.001	Significant
Within Groups	73.775		

*Significant at alpha = 0.05 (2-tailed)

From the presentation of analysis in Table 3.0 in interest factor, it could be deduced that the respondents' level of motivation towards learning social studies in virtual environment shows significantly differ when data are grouped according to year level. This means that year levels in interest factor are factor influencing significant difference on the level of motivation of students this means that students have. According to Ryan et al (2002), student interest are characterized on their year level, and year level greatly affects the level of interest and motivation of the child, conversely, the more higher the year level, the more interest that student would spend on their learning.

Table 3.1: Academic Level of Motivation when group according to Year Level across Confidence factor

	Mean Square	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
Between Groups	9.571	.005	Significant
Within Groups	86.966		

*Significant at alpha = 0.05 (2-tailed)

The data analysis presented in Table 3.1 in confidence factor, shows that students confidence have something to do with their year level since it shows that there is a significance difference between year levels of the respondents' in terms of confidence factor in the level of motivation towards learning social studies in virtual environment. it can be deduced that students confidence are boosting up once they are on a current state of year levels, the higher their year level, the more confidence they are putting into their learning.

Conversely, students prioritize confidence as it is a stepping stone and a vital ingredients for academic success to be able to move forward to a higher and complex year level. This was in consonant to the study conducted by Ryan and Deci (2002), that in each year level students shows different types of confidence across the social studies curriculum and it became more positive when students are praise and tag with good job by their respective teachers. Moreover, Ryan and Deci (2002), have stated that building up of self-efficacy are related to year levels, that is why year levels is a factor when it comes to confidence in learning social studies in a virtual environment.

Table 3.2: Academic Level of Motivation when group according to Year Level across Information Acquisition factor

	Mean Square	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
Between Groups	6.203	.032	Not Significant
Within Groups	83.007		

*Significant at alpha = 0.05 (2-tailed)

The data presented in Table 3.2 in information acquisition factor, it could be conclude that the respondents' level of motivation towards learning social studies in virtual environment shows not significantly differ when data are grouped according to year level. Which means that year levels in information acquisition is not a factor influencing significant difference on the level of motivation of students, it can be infer that students have a different information being acquired at the same time, and different ways of acquiring it and not affected by their year level. In the study conducted by Foskett et al. (2004), student information acquisition are the ways they acquired information regarding a certain task, and every student have a different ways of gathering data depending on their learning preference and of course the subject that they are taking with.

Table 3.3: Academic Level of Motivation when group according to Year Level across Performance factor

	Mean Square	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
Between Groups	7.806	.011	Not Significant
Within Groups	81.648		

*Significant at alpha = 0.05 (2-tailed)

The data analysis presented in Table 3.3 in performance factor, it could be conclude that year levels do not affect and do not differ when it comes to the respondents' level of motivation towards learning social studies in virtual environment. Which means that year levels in performance is not a factor influencing significant difference on the level of motivation of students, it can be infer that students have a variety of performance being shown on their respective classes and subject areas. This was similar to the study conducted by Lee. (2017), that in each year level students excel different types of performance across the social studies curriculum and most of them are from easy to difficult performance that is why year levels are not a factor when it comes to performance in learning social studies.

Table 3.4: Academic Level of Motivation when group according to Year Level across Overall factor

	Mean Square	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
Between Groups	8.090	.004	Significant
Within Groups	68.904		

*Significant at alpha = 0.05 (2-tailed)

The data analysis presented in Table 3.3 in overall level of motivation, it shows that year levels in the overall factors of motivation that constitutes interest, confidence, information acquisition and performance, significantly affect and differ the respondents level of motivation towards learning social studies in virtual environment. Moreover, two of the factors got significant difference namely: interest and confidence, on the other hand, the two other factor: information acquisition and performance has an interpretation of not significant. The researcher conclude that students interest and confidence are

more ignited and practice in the new normal while the other two information acquisition and performance are factors that individuals possess and differ in terms of their connection accessibility, learning space and more. This was in consonant with the findings of Renninger et al. (2016), wherein they stated the factors that could make the subscale differ such as the information acquisition, factors such as inability to access internet connection, types of devices, and learning environment.

V. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

As mentioned before, the main purpose of this research is to distinguish the level of motivation of the respondents towards studying social studies in a virtual environment in terms of interest, confidence, information acquisition and performance, and to find out if there a significant difference on student's level of motivation when they are group according to their gender, and year level. In order to analyze the results, the researcher utilized descriptive statistics for the instruments to find out the level of motivation in terms of four factors mentioned above; moreover the researcher also utilized parametric statistics, independent samples T-test to discern if there is a significance difference on gender, and one-way ANOVA to determine if there is a significance difference on year level. After performing statistical test, overall the result shows that the respondents shows 'High Motivation' (M= 4.06, SD- 0.78) among the four factors: interest, confidence, information acquisition and performance.

Furthermore, for the significance difference on gender, it implies that there is no significant difference (sig. value = 0.235 > $\alpha = 0.05$) in the overall factor towards learning social studies in a virtual environment when respondents are grouped according to their gender. Moreover, for the significance difference on year level, the results shows that two of the factors namely interest and confidence indicates 'significant difference' when respondents are grouped based on their year level. On the other hand, the other two factor namely, information acquisition and performance has an interpretation of 'not significant'. The findings absolutely signifies that the respondents shows 'High Motivation' and are still motivated amidst the challenges brought by the pandemic. Respondents shows that interest, confidence, information acquisition and performance still sparks even in the virtual learning environment. It was also noted that the virtual learning or online learning helps the respondents to continue their interest in learning, to gain more confidence, to have adequate information with the use of the internet and to improve their academic performance.

The result yields that teachers and other stakeholders must keep this generation of learners motivated. And so, the educational institutions such as Western Mindanao State University must continue to improve its educational system and to continue developing the mode of online learning to cater the needs of the students in order to nurture and flourish the motivation of the learners towards learning social studies and other disciplines virtually while we are still experiencing pandemic.

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